

Densities and viscosities of binary mixtures of acetonitrile with alkanols (C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈, C₁₀) at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K

Pandharinath S. Nikam^{a*}, Laxman N. Shirsat^b and Mehdi Hasan^a

^aP. G. Department of Physical Chemistry, M. S. G. College, Malegaon Camp-423 105, India

^bArts, Science and Commerce College, Deola (Nasik)-423 102, India

Manuscript received 3 November 1999, accepted 1 February 2000

Density and viscosity of binary mixtures of acetonitrile with pentan-1-ol, hexan-1-ol, heptan-1-ol, octan-1-ol and decan-1-ol have been measured at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K. The experimental values of densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) are used to calculate excess molar volumes (V^E) and deviations in viscosity ($\Delta\eta$). The V^E and $\Delta\eta$ are fitted to Redlich-Kister polynomial.

The effect of molecular size, shape and molecular association of alkanols on volumetric, viscometric and acoustic properties of binary mixtures containing alcohols have been reported by us^{1,2}. Viscosity and density of binary liquid mixtures are extensively used to understand molecular interactions between the components of the mixture, to develop new theoretical models and also for engineering applications. Acetonitrile, alkanols and their binary mixtures are often used as solvent³. In continuation of our earlier work⁴, we now report measurements of densities and viscosities of binary mixtures of acetonitrile with long-chain alkanols (C₅, C₆, C₇, C₈, C₁₀) at three different temperatures.

Results and Discussion

The experimental density (ρ) values (Table 1) have been used to calculate the excess molar volume (V^E) using the equation,

$$V^E = (M_1x_1 + M_2x_2)/\rho_{\text{mix}} - M_1x_1/\rho_1 - M_2x_2/\rho_2 \quad (1)$$

where ρ_{mix} is the density of the mixture and M_1 , M_2 , x_1 , x_2 and ρ_1 , ρ_2 are the molecular weight, mole fraction, and density of pure components 1 and 2, respectively. Excess volumes calculated from eqn. (2) are listed in Table 1. The results of V^E were fitted to a polynomial of the type,

$$V^E = x_1x_2 \sum a_i(x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (2)$$

where a_i is the number of coefficients. In each case, the optimum number of coefficients is ascertained from an examination of the variation in standard deviation (σ) as given by

$$\sigma = [\sum (X_{\text{obs}} - X_{\text{cal}})^2 / (n - m)]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where n is the total number of data points and m the number of coefficients considered. The coefficients and standard deviations for V^E as computed from eqns. (2) and (3), respectively, are presented in Table 2.

The viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) are obtained by

$$\Delta\eta = \eta_{\text{mix}} - x_1\eta_1 - x_2\eta_2 \quad (4)$$

where η_{mix} is viscosity of mixture and x_1 , x_2 and η_1 , η_2 are the mole fraction and viscosity of pure components 1 and 2, respectively. The coefficients, a_i , and standard deviation, σ , for $\Delta\eta$ as obtained from eqns. (2) and (3) are listed in Table 2. Estimated uncertainties were $\pm 0.005 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in V^E and $\pm 0.005 \text{ mPa s}$ in $\Delta\eta$. Excess molar volumes are positive for mixtures of acetonitrile with all the alkanols (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Excess molar volumes (V^E) at 298.15 K for x_1 acetonitrile + $(1-x_1)$ alkanols: (●) pentan-1-ol, (■) hexan-1-ol, (⊗) heptan-1-ol, (○) octan-1-ol, (□) decan-1-ol

The excess Gibbs free energy of flow (G^{*E}) has been calculated from the viscosity and density data using expression,

$$G^{*E} = RT \{ \ln \eta V - x_1 \ln \eta_1 V_1 - x_2 \ln \eta_2 V_2 \} \quad (5)$$

Table 1. Densities (ρ), excess molar volumes (V^E) and viscosities (η) for acetonitrile (1) + alkanols (2) at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K

x_1	298.15 K			303.15 K			308.15 K		
	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ kg mol ⁻¹	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	η mPa s	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ kg mol ⁻¹	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	η kg mol ⁻¹	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ kg mol ⁻¹	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	η mPa s
Acetonitrile (1) + Pentanol (2)									
0.0000	0.81108	–	3.510	0.80733	–	2.961	0.80351	–	2.518
0.1083	0.80892	0.027	2.485	0.80491	0.048	1.966	0.80093	0.055	1.752
0.1933	0.80693	0.062	1.918	0.80291	0.073	1.703	0.79880	0.084	1.519
0.2503	0.80561	0.070	1.717	0.80152	0.082	1.477	0.79734	0.093	1.334
0.3407	0.80320	0.098	1.330	0.79902	0.108	1.200	0.79462	0.130	1.088
0.4797	0.79917	0.114	0.963	0.79474	0.130	0.879	0.79008	0.156	0.804
0.5899	0.79560	0.107	0.747	0.79098	0.124	0.688	0.78612	0.149	0.636
0.6833	0.79217	0.094	0.619	0.78744	0.124	0.569	0.78234	0.132	0.527
0.7642	0.78887	0.073	0.525	0.78392	0.088	0.486	0.77875	0.104	0.458
0.8347	0.78559	0.056	0.452	0.78052	0.066	0.428	0.77519	0.080	0.410
0.8958	0.78246	0.036	0.418	0.77724	0.045	0.392	0.77184	0.049	0.369
0.9508	0.77934	0.016	0.374	0.77398	0.023	0.357	0.76845	0.024	0.342
1.0000	0.77622	–	0.342	0.77080	–	0.326	0.76518	–	0.306
Acetonitrile (1) + Hexanol (2)									
0.0000	0.81537	–	4.592	0.81189	–	3.765	0.80812	–	3.300
0.1095	0.81301	0.062	3.187	0.80930	0.081	2.576	0.80531	0.100	2.165
0.2173	0.81028	0.133	2.358	0.80646	0.152	2.078	0.80239	0.166	1.839
0.2885	0.80842	0.159	1.966	0.80381	0.191	1.831	0.80032	0.197	1.573
0.3844	0.80560	0.194	1.550	0.80155	0.214	1.386	0.79727	0.229	1.233
0.5121	0.80143	0.212	1.109	0.79720	0.228	1.004	0.79271	0.245	0.913
0.6270	0.79715	0.198	0.840	0.79270	0.214	0.766	0.78805	0.225	0.704
0.7147	0.79339	0.172	0.676	0.78876	0.186	0.611	0.78393	0.196	0.570
0.7903	0.78970	0.141	0.545	0.78484	0.158	0.513	0.77986	0.163	0.483
0.8533	0.78628	0.103	0.470	0.78124	0.177	0.445	0.77610	0.121	0.419
0.9086	0.78293	0.063	0.415	0.77773	0.074	0.395	0.77245	0.075	0.376
0.9558	0.77963	0.033	0.377	0.77434	0.037	0.360	0.76883	0.042	0.343
1.0000	0.77622	–	0.342	0.77080	–	0.326	0.76518	–	0.306
Acetonitrile (1) + Heptan-1-ol (2)									
0.0000	0.82079	–	5.937	0.81715	–	4.996	0.81353	–	4.176
0.0959	0.81840	0.112	3.772	0.81462	0.125	3.561	0.81070	0.162	2.881
0.2368	0.81460	0.233	2.953	0.81065	0.252	2.592	0.80668	0.274	2.277
0.3327	0.81172	0.286	2.267	0.80771	0.299	2.022	0.80351	0.337	1.808
0.4126	0.80909	0.316	1.836	0.80483	0.350	1.634	0.80059	0.377	1.457
0.5459	0.80406	0.338	1.278	0.79956	0.375	1.149	0.79505	0.407	1.407
0.6546	0.79935	0.310	0.943	0.79468	0.341	0.857	0.78992	0.375	0.786
0.7410	0.79489	0.274	0.716	0.79011	0.296	0.658	0.78516	0.325	0.611
0.8119	0.79080	0.218	0.580	0.78589	0.234	0.547	0.78080	0.255	0.510
0.8706	0.78679	0.173	0.487	0.78191	0.171	0.463	0.77665	0.188	0.433
0.9199	0.78334	0.102	0.423	0.77815	0.108	0.402	0.77273	0.122	0.382
0.9633	0.77954	0.058	0.384	0.77422	0.063	0.366	0.76866	0.072	0.350
1.0000	0.77622	–	0.342	0.77080	–	0.326	0.76518	–	0.306
Acetonitrile (1) + Octan-1-ol (2)									
0.0000	0.82158	–	7.365	0.81805	–	6.125	0.81443	–	5.274
0.1277	0.81840	0.160	5.028	0.81442	0.196	4.029	0.81091	0.219	3.493
0.2608	0.81512	0.270	3.533	0.81134	0.279	3.090	0.80744	0.291	2.688
0.3381	0.81281	0.327	2.848	0.80871	0.373	2.530	0.80471	0.387	2.203
0.4447	0.80912	0.399	2.086	0.80509	0.414	1.862	0.80101	0.420	1.638
0.5793	0.80372	0.434	1.427	0.79951	0.445	1.282	0.79512	0.463	1.151
0.6800	0.79896	0.412	1.028	0.79454	0.425	0.927	0.78991	0.446	0.840
0.7638	0.79438	0.358	0.770	0.78971	0.375	0.701	0.78486	0.396	0.647
0.8283	0.79026	0.300	0.695	0.78544	0.312	0.562	0.78041	0.330	0.523
0.8825	0.78645	0.225	0.502	0.78151	0.230	0.472	0.77631	0.244	0.446
0.9273	0.78297	0.146	0.435	0.77780	0.154	0.414	0.77241	0.167	0.391
0.9670	0.77956	0.063	0.390	0.77415	0.075	0.364	0.76861	0.083	0.346
1.0000	0.77622	–	0.342	0.77080	–	0.326	0.76518	–	0.306

Acetonitrile (1) + Decan-1-ol (2)									
0.0000	0.82632	–	11.568	0.82277	–	9.552	0.81914	–	7.908
0.0939	0.82412	0.175	8.794	0.82045	0.190	7.622	0.81656	0.236	6.471
0.2005	0.82132	0.350	6.554	0.81755	0.371	5.660	0.81353	0.427	4.934
0.3010	0.81852	0.455	4.932	0.81471	0.466	4.226	0.81079	0.483	3.648
0.3902	0.81557	0.544	3.872	0.81154	0.580	3.394	0.80739	0.620	2.877
0.4935	0.81170	0.607	2.848	0.80756	0.639	2.467	0.80328	0.677	2.150
0.6249	0.80584	0.611	1.830	0.80131	0.665	1.678	0.79673	0.711	1.441
0.7216	0.80067	0.543	1.302	0.79594	0.592	1.189	0.79113	0.635	1.053
0.7933	0.79613	0.452	1.021	0.79123	0.494	0.864	0.78613	0.543	0.777
0.8544	0.79165	0.341	0.790	0.78650	0.383	0.636	0.78126	0.421	0.586
0.9006	0.78744	0.262	0.548	0.78222	0.291	0.510	0.77688	0.317	0.479
0.9382	0.78367	0.173	0.460	0.77848	0.184	0.431	0.77288	0.213	0.411
0.9708	0.78026	0.064	0.395	0.77466	0.092	0.379	0.76883	0.122	0.358
1.0000	0.77622	–	0.342	0.77080	–	0.326	0.76518	–	0.306

Table 2. Parameters and standard deviations (σ) of eqns. (3) and (4) for acetonitrile + alkanols

System	Temp. K	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	σ
Acetonitrile V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹) + pentan-1-ol	298.15	0.4563	0.0008	-0.1994	0.0831	–	–	0.003
	303.15	0.4887	0.0339	-0.0092	-0.0487	–	–	0.005
	308.15	0.5964	0.0982	-0.0828	-0.1663	–	–	0.005
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	298.15	-4.0925	2.2403	-0.0615	-0.8498	-2.1343	2.5896	0.013
	303.15	-3.3131	1.6394	1.0987	-1.1061	-5.7900	5.8834	0.023
	308.15	-2.6402	1.2173	0.9309	-1.0893	-4.1223	4.6364	0.015
Acetonitrile V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹) + hexan-1-ol	298.15	0.8420	0.0416	-0.0898	0.0996	-0.1725	–	0.003
	303.15	0.9063	-0.0034	0.1492	0.0975	-0.3351	–	0.003
	308.15	0.9747	0.0238	-0.0948	-0.1147	0.1991	–	0.003
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	298.15	-5.2305	2.5483	-1.9330	1.9203	-0.8519	–	0.009
	303.15	-4.0813	1.6234	0.8489	-0.2143	-5.6789	5.0959	0.009
	308.15	-3.4326	0.3573	0.1397	5.4922	-5.1514	–	0.045
Acetonitrile V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹) + heptan-1-ol	298.15	1.3472	0.1397	-0.1000	-0.0210	0.2745	–	0.006
	303.15	1.5060	0.2052	-0.5825	-0.2086	0.7047	–	0.009
	308.15	1.6476	0.2854	-0.7275	-0.5589	1.5005	–	0.008
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	298.15	-13.3065	0.5060	-2.3756	0.3582	–	–	0.067
	303.15	-5.4012	1.4741	-1.2561	4.7006	-3.3370	–	0.036
	308.15	-4.2114	0.661	-0.3717	6.7199	-5.4857	–	0.054
Acetonitrile V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹) + octan-1-ol	298.15	1.6357	0.7097	0.5191	-0.4404	-0.4992	–	0.009
	303.15	1.7418	0.6723	0.1375	-0.6317	0.5003	–	0.012
	308.15	1.8023	0.7626	0.1200	-0.8878	0.9172	–	0.014
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	298.15	-8.1760	3.1979	-2.4372	2.1034	-0.3560	–	0.023
	303.15	-6.3959	1.1639	-1.2091	6.4144	-4.9449	–	0.043
	308.15	-5.3958	1.0768	-1.1441	5.3433	-3.8809	–	0.039
Acetonitrile V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹) + decan-1-ol	298.15	2.3645	0.6870	0.8736	-0.3625	-1.2258	–	0.016
	303.15	2.5790	0.8212	0.1859	-0.3878	0.0273	–	0.011
	308.15	2.7927	0.8623	-0.4733	-0.5469	1.7655	–	0.022
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	298.15	12.7311	5.4268	-1.8967	1.5063	2.3276	–	0.032
	303.15	-9.8756	4.6875	-3.4527	-2.9965	4.2313	–	0.034
	308.15	-7.9885	3.1753	-1.0749	-2.9247	2.9390	–	0.024

in which the terms have their usual meaning. The observed G^*E values at 298.15 K are represented in Fig. 2.

The observed positive excess molar volume values in the present investigation may be discussed in terms of several effects⁵. These may be divided into three types :

chemical, physical and structural. Changes in the associative equilibria of alkan-1-ol molecules may lead to contributions of all three types. The disruption of alkanol aggregates through the breaking of H-bonds makes V^E positive, since aggregates have smaller volumes than the sum

of their components. Calculations indicate that contribution of H-bond breaking to V^E is negligible in high concentration region of alkanols. There is relatively strong association of alkan-1-ols at room temperature. For the dilute alkanol region, where the degree of association is low, the breaking of H-bond is more, making positive contribution to V^E . The physical effects involving dispersive forces between the real species present in the mixture also contribute to positive V^E . It is observed that these dispersive forces comprise the major part of the positive contributions

Fig. 2. G^E values at 298.15 K for x_1 acetonitrile + $(1-x_1)$ alkanols (○) pentan-1-ol, (◐) hexan-1-ol, (⊗) heptan-1-ol, (◑) octan-1-ol, (◒) decan-1-ol

to V^E over much of the mole fraction range. The negative V^E arise from several contributions, involving specific interactions, interstitial accommodation and change of free volume, which seem to be probably absent in the present investigation. The increase in V^E with increase in chain-length of alkanols implies that acetonitrile-alkanol interaction is relatively weaker due to the less proton-donating ability of higher alkanols than the lower ones. Thus the mixtures of acetonitrile with alkanols (C₅-C₁₀) show the trends in V^E values as decan-1-ol > octan-1-ol > heptan-1-ol > hexan-1-ol > pentan-1-ol.

There is a systematic increase in V^E with a rise in temperature for all mixtures. However, such changes are small and therefore not included in Fig. 1 to avoid congestion of data points. This increase in V^E with temperature is as expected from theoretical considerations⁶.

Deviations in viscosity ($\Delta\eta$) for the mixtures of acetonitrile with alkanols (C₅-C₁₀) are negative (Fig. 3)

Fig. 3. $\Delta\eta$ values at 298.15 K for x_1 acetonitrile + $(1-x_1)$ alkanols (○) pentan-1-ol, (◐) hexan-1-ol, (⊗) heptan-1-ol, (◑) octan-1-ol, (◒) decan-1-ol

which decrease with increasing size of alkanols. The trend in $\Delta\eta$ is pentan-1-ol > hexan-1-ol > heptan-1-ol > octan-1-ol > decan-1-ol. The dominance of endothermic enthalpy of mixing over exothermic mixing resulting acetonitrile-alkanol interaction, leads to more negative $\Delta\eta$ values for higher alkanols than for lower ones⁷. It seems that in acetonitrile-alkanol systems, the forces between pairs of unlike molecules are far less than the forces between pairs of like molecules. Therefore, the binary mixtures of acetonitrile with lower alkanols are less fluid due to enhanced intermolecular forces resulting from higher proton-donating ability of lower alkanols or due to filling of voids of acetonitrile with small molecules of lower alkanols. Negative $\Delta\eta$ values in the present investigation can also be attributed to unequal molecular sizes of the constituent molecules of the mixture where dispersion forces are dominant⁸. The effect of temperature increase is to disrupt hetero and homo associations of molecules which causes increase in fluidity of the liquid. Therefore, $\Delta\eta$ values are higher at higher temperatures.

The negative values of excess Gibbs free energy of flow for acetonitrile-pentanol over the entire range of composition and temperature indicate either complex formation or interstitial accommodation of small pentanol molecules in the voids of acetonitrile, the second possibility being more probable. In all other systems, G^E values are positive indicating dominance of dispersive forces over specific interactions between acetonitrile-alkanol molecules.

Experimental

Acetonitrile (E. Merck, 99.5% pure) and alkanols (E. Merck, 99.7% pure) were purified². Purity of the solvents (99.7%) was ascertained by GLC and constancy of their boiling temperatures and also by comparing their densities and viscosities with the literature values at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K. Procedure adopted for preparation of binary mixtures was the same as reported earlier⁴. Mixtures of acetonitrile with alkanols were prepared by mass in air-tight stoppered glass bottles to avoid evaporation and contamination during the mixing process. The possible error in mole fraction was estimated to be less than $\pm 1 \times 10^4$.

A double-arm pycnometer with a bulb (15 cm^3) and a capillary (i.d. $\sim 1 \text{ mm}$) was used to measure densities of binary liquid mixtures as reported earlier^{9,10}. The density values were reproducible within $\pm 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. The viscosity of binary liquid mixtures was measured with two suspended level Ubbelohde viscometers calibrated with triple-distilled water⁴. The viscometers with minimum flow times of 138.18 and 103.12 s for acetonitrile, were used. At least three repeat of each data set reproducible to $\pm 0.5 \text{ s}$ for alkanols $\text{C}_5\text{-C}_8$ and 2 s for alkanol C_{10} were obtained and the results averaged. Since all flow times were greater than 100 s, and capillary radius (0.5 mm) far less than its length (50–60 mm), the kinetic energy and end-corrections,

respectively, were found to be negligible. The accuracy in viscosity measurements was $\pm 0.001 \text{ mPa s}$ for alkanols $\text{C}_5\text{-C}_8$ and $\pm 0.005 \text{ mPa s}$ for C_{10} alkanol.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Principal, M. S. G. College, Malegaon Camp, for facilities.

References

1. P. S. Nikam, M. C. Jadhav and M. Hasan, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 1998, **76**, 1.
2. P. S. Nikam, T. R. Mahale and M. Hasan, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1998, **43**, 436.
3. J. Barthel, H. J. Gores, G. Schmeer and R. Wachter, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 1983, **1**, 33.
4. P. S. Nikam, L. N. Shirsat and M. Hasan, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1998, **43**, 732.
5. A. J. Treszczanowicz, O. Kiyohara and G. C. Benson, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1981, **13**, 253.
6. T. M. Aminabhavi and B. Gopalkrishna, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1994, **39**, 529.
7. T. M. Aminabhavi and S. K. Raikar, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1993, **38**, 310.
8. R. J. Fort and H. Moore, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, **61**, 2102.
9. P. S. Nikam and A. B. Sawant, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn*, 1998, **71**, 2055.
10. P. S. Nikam, T. R. Mahale and M. Hasan, *Acustica*, 1998, **84**, 579.